

METHODOLOGICAL FEATURES OF USING THE GAME METHOD IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION LESSONS

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ABSTRACT: This article reveals the game method necessary in physical education lessons in primary school, which is one of the important means of comprehensive education of children. Its characteristic feature is the complexity of its impact on the body from all sides: the game simultaneously provides physical, mental, moral, aesthetic and labor education. In the process of physical education, the game method contributes to the comprehensive improvement of movements and physical qualities, since it contains favorable prerequisites for the development of dexterity, strength, speed, and endurance.

Key words: game method, physical qualities, junior schoolchild, game, physical exercises.

Children of primary school age are particularly mobile and have a constant need for movement. But when choosing games, the teacher must take into account that the body of younger schoolchildren is not ready to tolerate long strains. Therefore, games should not be very long; It is absolutely necessary to stop for a holiday.

Children 7-9 years old (pupils in grades 1-3) have all types of natural movements (walking, running, jumping, throwing), still not technically enough, so outdoor games are associated with natural movements and should occupy a huge place in them. Mastering skills and abilities at this age is more effective at the level of involuntary memorization (in particular, in games) than voluntarily. In addition, it is necessary to take into account the anatomical, physiological and psychological characteristics of children of this age. They have great compliance with various environmental impacts and rapid fatigue.

This is due to the fact that the heart, lungs and vascular system in children of this age are lagging behind in development, and the muscles are still weak, in particular the back and abdominal muscles. The strength of the supporting apparatus is also still

is not great, and, therefore, the possibility of its damage increases (muscle weakness, overextensibility of the ligaments increases the possibility of poor posture). More suitable games for children of this age are running games, for example, "Wolf in the Moat," in which children, after a short dash, have the opportunity to relax, or games with alternating roles played in motion, such as "Empty Space."

During this period, children still find it difficult to isolate individual movements and precisely regulate their individual characteristics. Children soon become tired as soon as they regain their readiness to move.

The attention of children of primary school age is not stable enough, and therefore outdoor games do not have to require long-term attention from them. The will and inhibitory functions of children are poorly developed; it is difficult for them to listen to explanations of the game for a long time and to explanations to the end.

It should be borne in mind that children of this age can already read and write, which significantly expands their mental horizons, for example, the games “Geese-Swans”, “Two Frosts”, “Owl”. In collective games, the simplest ideas about norms of behavior are put forward. The role and significance of games should occupy a huge place in the lives of children of primary school age, as this corresponds to their age characteristics. Physical education lessons in grades 1-4 can consist exclusively of outdoor games. A lesson consisting of games requires organized behavior and some gaming skills from the student. In physical education lessons for younger students, it is recommended to conduct from 3 to 5 games: in the preparatory part - games with low mobility, mainly - 2 - 3 games of high mobility, in the final part - games for developing attention and low intensity.

Games that improve the balance and coordination abilities of the participants are best given in the first half of the main part of the lesson, until attention is weakened by fatigue; game challenges and endurance relay races after games to improve coordination and speed. From time to time in the lower grades you can conduct a lesson - a competition, i.e. a lesson that consists exclusively of outdoor games and various relay races.

In order to effectively conduct outdoor games with primary schoolchildren, the teacher needs to take into account the conditions, preparedness and age characteristics of the students, as well as the pedagogical objectives of the lesson. Before you begin to explain the game, you need to place the participants in such a way that they can clearly see the teacher and hear his story.

It is best to line up the players in the starting position from which they will start the game. If the game is played in a circle, then the explanation is in the same

circular design. The teacher takes a place not in the center, but among the players. If the players are divided into two teams and lined up at a large distance, then for an explanation it is necessary to bring the teams closer, and then let the team move to the start boundaries. In this case, the teacher, explaining the game, stands between the players in the middle of the court, on the side border

and turns to one or the other team.

It should be remembered that the presentation of the game must be accompanied by a show. Visibility helps to better understand the game, and after the explanation, participants will have no questions. The teacher should stand in a visible place, sideways or, in extreme cases, facing the light, but in order to see all the participants and monitor their behavior.

Explanation of the game. Proper explanation of the game greatly influences its success. As already mentioned, before starting the game, the teacher must clearly visualize his content, analyze it in advance and only then begin to explain.

The rules should be brief: a lengthy explanation can interfere with the perception of the game. The exception is games in the lower grades, which can be explained in a fabulous, exciting way. The rule must be logical and consistent. Any game should be explained roughly according to this scheme: a) the name of the game (you can say for what purpose the game is played);

- b) the roles of the players and their location on the field;
- c) game content;
- d) the goal of the game;
- e) rules of the game[4].

The explanation of the game ends with answers to the players' questions. Answer

must be loud while addressing everyone at the same time. Speaking about the progress of the game,

The teacher will undoubtedly touch on the rules, but at the end of the rules you need to focus your attention again so that the children understand them better. The rules should not be spoken monotonously; it is advisable to highlight important points in Game.

The teacher must pay attention to the mood of the students: if they are distracted, the rules of the game must be reduced. The contents of the game are explained in detail only when students play it for the first time. When repeating the game, you just need to remind the main content and explain additional rules and methods.

The teacher must establish an order in the game in which each child must lead the game (be its captain) in turn. You can assign it in different ways:

- As directed by the teacher.
- There is a method of choosing by lot.
- Fairly establish consistency in the selection of commanders, so that every participant can become one. This promotes development organizational skills and activities.
- You can assign a guide based on the results of previous games.

The player who turns out to be the most mobile, fastest, etc. becomes the leading player in the previous game. But this must be communicated to the participants in advance so that they strive to show the necessary qualities

in games. The negative side of this method is that weaker and less dexterous children will not be able to become a captain.

Distribution for teams can also be done in various ways:

a) the teacher distributes players into teams at his own discretion in cases where it is necessary to assemble teams of equal strength. This method is most often used in complex outdoor and sports games;

b) another way to distribute players in teams is to line up students and calculate for the first or second: the first numbers will be one team, the second will be the other team. This quick distribution is useful for the lesson because it is time-limited, but its disadvantage is that the teams are not always equal in strength;

c) you can divide the players into teams using a figure march or calculation of a moving column. Each line should have as many people as required for the game. This method also does not require much time, but the composition of the teams is random and often unequal in strength;

d) the method of dividing teams by agreement is also used. In this case, the children choose captains, divided into pairs (roughly equal in strength), distribute who will be who, and the captains choose them by their names. With this division, the teams are almost always equal in strength. Children love this path very much, because this distribution is a game in itself. However, its disadvantage is that it cannot be used in lessons: it takes a lot of time;

e) method of segregation by appointment of captains. Players choose two captains, who in turn recruit players to their team.

This is a fairly fast method and the teams are mostly equal in strength. The negative side of this method is that captains are reluctant to accept weak players, which often leads to insults and quarrels among the players. To avoid unpleasant situations, it is recommended not

to make a choice until the end and divide the remaining ones into calculations. The method of appointing captains should only be used in games with high school age players who can correctly judge the strength of the players. playing field. The teacher announces the assignment of assistants to everyone who plays. Depending on the complexity of the game and the tasks that need to be solved during the lessons, assistants can explain the rules during the game.

Game control is extremely important. The importance of skillful management of the game process was emphasized by P. F. Lesgaft. According to him, the teacher “must understand the meaning of the rules themselves and not allow arbitrariness in their thoughts and actions and always be able ... to remain completely objective in relation to the students ... through the game they are accustomed to independent activity ... it is necessary, so that they themselves lead the game and control the exact implementation of the accepted rules.” The game must begin in an organized and timely manner, according to the conventional signal (command, whistle, clapping, waving or turning over). Conditioned signals are best alternated so that children take into account the accuracy and speed of the motor reaction. The teacher warns the children in advance about the signal he has chosen and gives it only after he is convinced that all the players have understood the content of the game and have taken their places. After the game has started, the teacher carefully monitors its progress, the behavior of the players, corrects and comments, without stopping the overall progress of the game. If most players make the same mistake, they can pause the game and give instructions on how to perform the game's tricks correctly, paying attention to the tactics. At the same time, he gives children maximum initiative and remains an impartial and objective judge. If the outdoor game is complex, the teacher first introduces the children to the basic rules, and then gradually supplements them during the game. To signal the end of the game, it's best when everyone involved has enjoyed it without going overboard. The game cannot be stopped by shouting or a stern command, since such an unexpected end for students can cause a negative reaction and dissatisfaction.

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